

I have always imagined that Paradise
will be a kind of library.

-Jorge Luis Borges

Marketing to get better
mileage from your
resources

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- Marketing is the social process by which individuals and groups obtain what they need and want through creating and exchanging products and value with others (Philip Kotler)

Why do we need marketing?

Why should librarians do
the marketing?

“Is there a magic button
somewhere for us just to
push and market our e-
resources”?

“Legwork”

- Targeted groups, Customer groups, Competition, Marketing tools, Marketing surveys, feed back device, CRM, customer satisfaction, marketing environment, PEST analysis, SWOT analysis, Five Forces Analysis, Marketing research, Marketing strategy, Ansoff’s matrix, Boston matrix, Bowman’s Strategy, Poret’s Generic Strategies, Value chain, Segmentation, Positioning, Objectives, Profitability, Concept of marketing, Micro-environment

Difficult?

Internal and external
marketing
Different forum for
marketing

How to
market your resources
better and more proactively
both to the academic
community as whole and to
your own university
hierarchy.

How to:
give library staff an insight
into internal
and external marketing

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the 4 steps of old fashioned marketing

- analysis
- strategy and planning
- tactics and realization
- feedback

- SWOT analysis
- PEST Analysis
- Five Forces Analysis

SWOT audits organisations

- strengths
- weaknesses
- opportunities
- threats.

PEST Analysis audits organisations

- Political aspects
- Economical aspects
- Sociocultural aspects
- Technological aspects

Five Forces Analysis audits different threats

- like threat of entry
- the power of buyers
- the power of suppliers
- the threat of substitutes, and competitive rivalry

Strategy

Boston Matrix

Stars – products/services with high market growth and that are easy to maintain. Keep, and build, your stars.

Cash Cows – products/services with a high share of a slow growth market. They are good for the time being.

Dogs – products/services with a low share of a low growth market. Consider getting rid of these products in order to find time for new services.

Problem children – products/services which consume resources and generate little in return.

Ansoff's matrix

- Market Penetration
- Market Development
- Product Development
- Diversification

Realization (Do it)

There are different ways to make things happen, but we must be more proactive and also try to involve more staff.

How?

Costs – how can we justify
the costs

Who else can we
interest and involve so that they will help us?

Are we exploiting all our
resources?

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Even more visibility

Find time for marketing

Eliminate some routines,
and make your colleagues
do it as well

Paper

”All employees in an organisation are involved in the process of marketing and can either carry out or destroy the marketing”
Philip Kotler

There is no doubt that personal contact is extremely important and effective but it's not possible to use just that channel - which is why we must utilise other methods such as:

- (a) In the library's e-newsletter : almost all libraries have some kind of e-newsletter
- (b) In targeted email alerts sent to academics from our information specialists. This is ideal in theory, but unfortunately it usually tends to become just the general e-newsletter above, as we often put together all our news, because of lack of time. The problem is that our customers are overwhelmed by information and would like to have very tailored data -which we cannot provide because LACK OF TIME

- (c) Through e-mail to new staff giving useful links and introducing our services as the first in the university
- (d) Through training courses for staff and students. All libraries are using this marketing method. It is very important to have good people with an academic background and nice and pleasant approach there.

- (e) Through events associated with specific areas. Many libraries are very good at using all kind of events at the university to market themselves and their services. The trick is to have a good overview of what's happening around us
- (f) Through special programs like TDnet, Serial Solutions? Not many libraries are using these methods in the long run

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Zinnia H. H. H.

- (g) Through the institution's Website. Websites are of course very useful, but routines for regular checking and updating are very important, otherwise they could have a negative impact. A section with for instance New Resources is very much appreciated at many libraries.
- (h) Through Intranet: Usually tried in other types of libraries like governmental or cooperative. This used to be a very efficient way of marketing, but the glory of intranet tends to become at many organisations/companies less important than everybody hoped in the beginning

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- (i) Through an A-Z list with all serials extracted from Library Management system
- (j) Through "old fashioned" bookmarks in paper; which works very well and customers are coming and "asking" for these.
- (k) Through the library's own OPAC
- (l) Indirectly, through conversation on a related topic
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- (m) Many libraries are now reviewing all the library services and realize that they need to re-evaluate what should be provided, through internal & external marketing
- (n) Some libraries are very active and try to be involved in all university/organizational presentations to all the official visits
- (o) Through specific user sessions, organized from the library

- (p) Open house
- (q) Through different competitions
- (r) Through frequent contributions to the University bulletin.
- (s) Through Library workshops

- (t) Electronic monitor in the library
- (u) Publicity displays
- (v) Through leaflets (paper)
- (w) There was one library , who saw the opportunity for internal marketing at a library ball! It went very well and the library got many new users

Coordination of Marketing
efforts

“Word of mouth & personal
recommendations are
invaluable”

Most important!!!!

DO IT!

Do it again and again

- "Marketing is a learning game" (Philip Kotler)

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Feedback!!!!!!!!!!!!!!

